

3D DIC MEASUREMENT OF TUBULAR BRAIDED COMPOSITES

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Keywords: *tubular braided composites, strain measurement, digital image correlation*

1 Introduction

Tubular braided composites contain woven fibers which are cured in a resin matrix [1]. The material properties of braids can be altered by varying the fibers or resin materials [1, 2]. The stiffness of braided composites can also be altered by controlling the amount of matrix only regions in open-mesh braid configurations [3]. The ability to control material properties makes this an attractive manufacturing method for products that have specific stiffness requirements like the design rocket launch tubes, braided air ducts and aircraft support structures or medical applications like cardiovascular catheters [4, 5].

Tubular braided composites are manufactured using a Maypole braider [1, 2]. The braid preform architecture is varied by altering the speed of the braid mandrel or the fiber carrier speed [1].

In general, the material properties of composites are more difficult to determine than conventional engineering materials such as metals and plastics due to their inhomogeneous nature [6]. Material properties of braided composites have mostly been measured using either strain gauges or extensometers but these techniques do not describe the full field behavior of braided composites [6-8]. As well, there is limited experimental data, with small experimental variations or errors, for tubular braids [5]. Variations in longitudinal elastic modulus of 17.6% are typical for tubular braided composites [9].

A measurement technique is required that can measure the full behavior of braided composites so that material properties can be accurately be determined. Therefore a new contact-free imaging method has been developed to describe the behavior of open and closed mesh braided composites.

Optical measurement techniques have been applied to measurement of flat textile composites [10] and stereo imaging techniques have been applied to filament wound pressure vessels [11]. The behavior of braided tubular composites has been analyzed previously using a three dimensional digital image correlation technique (3D DIC) [12]. The study by Leung *et al.* [12] utilized two high resolution cameras and a stereo microscope to evaluate tubular braided allowing for a single unit cell to be viewed. A unit cell is assumed to represent the entire braid behavior [13]. All unit cells are assumed to have the same braid angle and have the same fiber and volume fractions. Material properties are also assumed to be constant for all braid unit cells [9, 14].

A new experimental setup is described to evaluate tubular braided composites. This method allows for numerous braid unit cells to be investigated describing the macro-scale behavior of tubular braided composites. The accuracy and repeatability of the contact free measurement technique will be assessed. As well, time dependency of tubular braided composites with a rigid thermoset matrix will be examined. The measurement of strain and changes to braid geometry due to applied tensile loads will be demonstrated. Finally, the longitudinal elastic modulus of tubular samples will be determined using strain calculated from 3D DIC optical measurements.

2 Methods

Braided Composite Manufacturing Process

The braided composite preforms were manufactured using a horizontal braider (Steege USA K80-72, Steeger USA, Inman, South Carolina). Kevlar fibers (Kevlar49, 5680 Denier, Dupont, Mississauga On, Canada) were used as the reinforcement material.

The braid preforms were placed over a 7/16" outer diameter polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) mandrel and impregnated with EPON 825 (Momentive Specialty Chemicals Inc., Columbus, OH) and Ancamine 1482 hardener (Air Products and Chemicals, Allentown, PA) thermoset resin mixed at a ratio of 100:19. The impregnated braid was cured in an oven at 110°C for 2 hours. The end tabs were bonded to be tubular braid samples using the same epoxy resin and curing process [12, 15-17]. Once the tubular braids were cured they were cut to length and then bonded to end tabs. All braids were cut to a length of 90mm [12].

Examples of tubular braid preforms and cured braids are presented in Fig. 1. The coordinate system associated with all braided structures is also shown. In this figure *y*-axis is defined as parallel to the long axis of the braid, *x*-axis positive to the right, and *z*-axis positive out of the page.

Testing Apparatus

The tubular braided composites were examined using the experimental setup shown in Fig. 2. The experimental setup allows for strain due to applied tensile loads to be measured as well as geometric changes to the braid geometry. Tensile loads were applied using a tensile frame (MTS, Eden Prairie, MN, USA). The MTS tensile frame was controlled with a data acquisition system (NI-USB 6211 DAQ, National Instruments, Austin, TX). Tensile loads applied to the tubular braids were measured using a load cell (1000 ± 15lb load cell, 661.12B, MTS, Eden Prairie, MN, USA) The tubular braids were imaged using two web cameras which have a 1920 x 1080 pixel array (Microsoft, LifeCam Studio, Redmond, WA). Samples were illuminated using an ultraviolet (UV) light emitting diode (LED) (UV (365 nm) Mounted High Power LED M365L2, ThorLabs, Newton NJ). The cameras were rotated around the sample using a motorized rotation stage (Thor Labs Continuous Rotation Stage with Stepper Motor, NR360S, Newton, NJ) to allow for strain measurements around the braid circumference instead of one static position. The motorized rotation stage is controlled by a stepper motor controller (ThorLabs apt Stepper Motor Controller, BSC201, Newton, NJ). Control of the MTS tensile frame, web cameras, rotation stage and UV LED is

achieved through a custom software program (MATLAB, 2009a, The Math Works, Natick, MA).

Three Dimensional Digital Image Correlation

Digital image correlation (DIC) is an optical measurement technique that measures displacement by comparing the gray scale intensity between reference and deformed image sets [18]. Three dimensional digital image correlation (3D DIC) allows for measurement of in-plane and out-of-plane displacement of an object [19, 20] through the use of two cameras.

The DIC measurement technique involves four main steps: (1) camera calibration (2) sample preparation (3) image collection (4) and image post processing [21]. Camera calibration converts from camera pixel space into test specimen physical space. The test specimen is prepared by applying a random speckle pattern to the surface; this is required to allow the DIC measurement technique to compare the grayscale intensity between the reference and deformed images to determine deformation. The tubular braid surface was first prepared by coating the surface with black spray paint (Indoor/Outdoor, Krylon Products Group, Cleveland, OH) to reduce the reflectivity of the braid surface. The speckle pattern was applied to the tubular braid samples using a high quality airbrush (Custom Micron B, Iwata Medea Inc., Portland, OR) and fluorescent paint 5404 Fluorescent Green Createx Airbrush Colors, Createx Colors, East Granby CT). A similar method for preparing samples was described by Leung *et al.* [12]. Once the speckle pattern is applied; images before and after deformation are collected and then post-processed to determine displacement and strain fields.

Collected images of the braid samples were processed using a commercial software package (DaVis version 8.0.8 StrainMaster 3D, LaVision GmbH, Gottingen, Germany) to measure displacement and strain. Displacement and strain will be measured around the braid circumference. The change in braid angle will also be optically measured using the 3D DIC optical measurement technique.

Loading Procedure

Tensile loads are applied to the tubular braid samples by displacing the MTS linear actuator in known increments. At each increment the load cell and MTS actuator position is recorded. Images around the circumference of the tubular braid are recorded by rotating the web cameras around the braid sample using the motorized rotation stage. Once the images are collected the MTS linear actuator will be displaced to the next position. A plot of the MTS actuator motion against increment number is shown in Fig. 3. This figure shows that the MTS actuator will move in increments at a specified rate of 1mm/min [3]. This sequence will continue until the maximum specified actuator displacement has been reached.

Images of the tubular braid samples were collected at four angles (0°, 30°, 60°, and 90°) around the braid circumference to assess variations in measured strains. Variations in strain of the tubular braids may be caused by non-uniform fiber distribution, voids in the epoxy matrix or off-axis loading of the tubular braid sample. Example images of a tubular braid sample at four angles are shown in Fig. 4 as well as the random speckle pattern applied using the airbrush and fluorescent paint.

Accuracy of 3D DIC Measurement

The accuracy of the 3D DIC measurement was assessed by displacing a tubular braid sample in known increments. A similar method for assessing the accuracy of 3D DIC was outlined by Haddadi *et al.* [22]. Displacement of the sample was achieved using the linear actuator of the MTS tensile frame. The sample was not fastened to the load cell allowing for the it to freely displace with the linear actuator. The sample was displaced a total distance of 1.7 mm over 20 increments. A total of 160 images were collected for each sample displacement test. This procedure was repeated 10 times for the same tubular braid sample.

Time Dependency of Tubular Braid Testing

Collection of images around the braid circumference requires a time delay to allow for the cameras to be rotated using the motorized rotation stage. To assess

any potential viscoelastic behavior three samples were imaged while applying a constant force of 918 ± 19 N using the MTS tensile frame. Images of the braid sample were collected at four angles (0°, 30°, 60°, and 90°) around the braid circumference. The cameras were rotated around the tubular braid 20 times for each sample to examine if the tubular braids exhibit viscoelastic behavior as a function of position around the braid circumference.

Braid Strain Measurement

A tubular braid sample will be assessed to examine the longitudinal and transverse strain pattern that occurs due to applied tensile loads. Strain will be examined along the profile of a line parallel to the longitudinal axis of the tubular braid. Measurement of strain along the tubular braid longitudinal axis will allow for the strain distribution along multiple unit cells to be examined.

Braid Geometry Measurement

The stereo images of the tubular braid samples were used to recreate the 3D braid surface using the 3D DIC optical measurement technique. The 3D braid surfaces were used to quantify the change in braid angle that occurs due to applied tensile loads. An example of a braid geometry recreated from the 3D DIC optical measurements is shown in Fig. 5. This figure shows the 3D braid surface before and after deformation (Fig. 5 (a) and (b) respectively). A distinct necking region can be seen for the braid in Fig. 5 (b) for an applied displacement of 1.7mm. The image of the 3D braid surfaces were created using a scientific visualization package (ParaView, Kitware, Inc. Clifton Park, New York).

A 2D projection of the braid surface was used to determine braid angle. A similar method for optically measuring braid angle was described by Leung [23]. Previously, braid angle has been measured by wrapping transparent paper onto the braid surface and using a protractor to measure braid angle [24]. The optical method also allows for braid angle to be measured before and after deformation of the tubular braid samples. The angle of the braid fibers was found by creating lines which are parallel to the braid fiber tows as shown in Fig. 6 (a). The

angle of the braid fibers was determined using the following equation:

$$\theta = \arctan\left(\frac{m_2 - m_1}{1 + m_1 \cdot m_2}\right) \quad (1)$$

Where m_1 and m_2 represent the slopes of the two fiber tows and θ is the angle between the two fiber tows. Braid angle is measured from the longitudinal axis of the tubular braid [15], therefore the measured braid angle from the longitudinal axis is equal to $\theta/2$. Fig. 6 (a) and (b) show the change in braid angle that occurred for a tubular braid sample and the determined braid angle change using Equation (1).

Longitudinal Elastic Modulus

The longitudinal elastic modulus of the tubular braided composite samples was determined using strain from the 3D DIC measurements of the tubular braid samples and from the load cell force measurements. For all braid samples a rectangular region of 10 x 20 mm was selected to determine the average longitudinal strain. An example of the rectangular region for strain calculation is shown in Fig. 7. The longitudinal elastic modulus will be determined at four angles (0°, 30°, 60°, and 90°) to determine if the longitudinal modulus varies around the braid circumference.

3 Results and Discussion

Accuracy of 3D DIC Measurement

The accuracy of the optical measurement of the tubular braid samples was assessed by displacing a tubular braid sample in known increments. The results of the displacement of the tubular braid sample are shown in Fig. 8. This figure shows that the correlated displacements for the tubular braid agree with the expected displacements. This figure also shows the maximum variation that occurred for the 10 replications. From this figure it can be seen that the maximum variation for the 3D DIC displacement measurements at each rotation position (0°, 30°, 60°, and 90°) are on the order of 0.015mm.

Time Dependency of Tubular Braid Testing

The results for the constant force test to assess viscoelastic behavior are shown in Fig. 9. Fig. 9 shows the displacement results measured using the 3D DIC measurement technique for the three tubular braid samples. This figure shows that the maximum displacement for the three samples is on the order of 0.005mm. Therefore the tubular braids manufactured with Kevlar49 fibers and EPON 825 / Ancamine 1482 resin do not exhibit a significant viscoelastic effect. As a result, the delay required to allow image collection around the braid circumference is expected to have little effect on the displacement or strain of the tubular braid samples.

Braid Strain Measurement

A tubular braid sample was assessed to examine the longitudinal and transverse strain pattern that occurs due to applied tensile loads. A representative strain pattern for a tubular braid sample for a maximum displacement of 1.7mm at the 0° position of the motorized rotation stage is shown in Fig. 10 and Fig. 11. The braid sample in Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 shows that necking occurred between the positions of 0 and 40mm along the y- axis. Fig. 10 (a) and Fig. 11 (a) show a two dimensional image of a tubular braid with a color map that represents the transverse and longitudinal strain that occurred for the tubular braid sample. An example profile line for the measurement of strain is also shown in these images.

The sub-figures (b - e) in Fig. 10 show the resulting transverse strain along the longitudinal axis of the tubular braid sample at the measured four angles (0°, 30°, 60°, and 90°). Similarly, sub-figures (b - e) in Fig. 11 show the resulting longitudinal strain along the longitudinal axis of the tubular braid sample at four angles. Sub-figures (b - e) for both Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 show the strain that occurs at 0.425, 0.85, 1.275 and 1.7 mm actuator stroke.

The sub-figures (b - e) for both Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 show that a periodic pattern occurs for the transverse and longitudinal strain between -20 and 20 mm along the longitudinal braid axis. A periodic strain pattern is expected for the tubular braid due to the repeating nature of the braid fiber tows. A diamond braid configuration was used in this study therefore the braid fibers form a “one-under-one-over pattern”. The cross-over between the two fiber

strands results in a periodic fiber pattern. A repeating strain pattern for flat textile composites has also been demonstrated by Ivanov et al [10]. Each of the sub-figures (b - e) show that strain increases in the braid sample as the displacement of the MTS linear actuator increases.

Strain measurements along the longitudinal axis of a tubular braid sample demonstrate the strain varies along the braid axis. Therefore, single point strain measurement devices like strain gauges or extensometers are not adequate for describing the strain behavior of tubular braids. Strain gauges have been shown to fail prematurely at 3% strain and the composites can exhibit shear deformation due to a scissoring effect of the fibers [6]. Matrix cracking can also occur for tubular braided composites under tensile loads [12]. As well measurement of a single braid unit cell is not sufficient to describe braid behavior as Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 show that strain varies along the longitudinal braid axis.

Braid Geometry Measurement

Tensile loads were applied to eight (8) tubular braid samples using the MTS tensile frame. The braid samples were displaced a total distance of 1.7mm in 20 increments and images were collected at 0°, 30°, 60°, and 90° around the braid sample. The 3D braid surface was recreated using the collected stereo images and the 3D DIC optical measurement technique. The braid angles before and after deformation were determined using Equation (1). The results for the maximum braid angle measurements for the 8 braid samples are shown in Table 1. Table 1 shows that the tubular braid samples had an original braid angle of $30.2 \pm 2.6^\circ$. As well the average braid angle change ($\Delta\theta$) was found to be $2.88 \pm 1.6^\circ$. The braid angle change of 2.88° indicates that the braid fibers have exhibited a scissoring effect as the resin matrix of the braids has failed [6]. Table 1 demonstrates that the braid angle change of the tubular braids varies around the circumference of the tubular braid samples.

The variation in the braid angle change around braid circumference may be due to inconsistencies in the manufacturing of the tubular braids. Variations in braid angle change may also be due to combined loading caused by misalignment between the end

tabs. Changes to braid angle are necessary to predict the material properties of tubular braided composites [12].

The tubular braid samples were also examined to determine the braid angle change prior to failure of the epoxy matrix. The results of braid angle change prior to failure are shown in Table 2. This table shows that the average braid angle change was $1.25 \pm 0.54^\circ$. Table 2 also shows that braid angle change varies around the braid circumference.

A similar braid angle change was determined by Leung *et al* [12] where a braid angle change of $0.8 \pm 0.33^\circ$ was found for tubular braids with an initial braid angle of $42.48 \pm 1.96^\circ$. The difference in braid angle change between this study and the study by Leung *et al* [12] may be due to the difference in initial braid angle.

Longitudinal Elastic Modulus

The longitudinal elastic modulus was determined for eight (8) tubular braid samples tested using the MTS tensile frame and 3D DIC optical measurement technique. The resulting elastic moduli are shown in Table 3. This table shows the variation in elastic modulus between braid samples as well as the variation with position around the braid circumference. This table shows that the maximum variation in longitudinal elastic modulus was 1.22 GPa. As well, Table 3 shows that the average longitudinal elastic modulus for the braid samples was 17.41 ± 3.52 GPa. The variation in longitudinal elastic modulus in this study has been found to be 20.2% of the mean value.

A study by Carey *et al.* [9] compared the predicted longitudinal elastic modulus using classical laminate plate theory (CLPT) and a modified CLPT model for tubular braids manufactured with Kevlar49/Ancamine1482. The CLPT model predicts a longitudinal elastic modulus of 25 GPa for a braid with a 30° braid angle while the generalized CLPT model predicts a longitudinal modulus of 15 GPa. Experimentally determined longitudinal elastic moduli for 50° tubular were found to have a variation of 17.6%. Therefore, similar results for tubular braided composites manufactured with

Kevlar49/ Ancamine1482 have been found by Carey *et al.* [9].

The variation in longitudinal elastic modulus could be reduced by manufacturing braids with more consistent braid angles. The tubular braids in this study we found to have a braid angle of $30.2 \pm 2.6^\circ$. The variation in initial braid angle will have an influence on the longitudinal elastic modulus [9].

5 Conclusions

A new experimental setup for evaluating tubular braided composites was developed. The experimental setup utilizes a stereo camera configuration and motorized rotation stage to capture the macroscopic tubular braided behavior. This method allows for numerous braid unit cells to be investigated.

In this study method for testing tubular braided composites has been described. The accuracy and repeatability of the experimental setup was evaluated. Finally, tubular braided composite samples were measured to determine the change in braid angle due to applied tensile loads and to determine the longitudinal elastic modulus for the braid samples.

The experimental setup has been evaluated to assess the accuracy of the 3D DIC optical measurements and to determine if the tubular braided composites used in this study exhibit viscoelastic behavior. The maximum variation for the 3D DIC displacement measurements were determined to be on the order of 0.015mm. As well, the tubular braided composites used in this study did not exhibit viscoelastic behavior for a constant applied load.

The resulting strain pattern for a tubular braided composite was determined using the 3D DIC optical measurement technique. The results demonstrate that strain varies along the braid axis. As well, optical measurement of a single braid unit cell is not sufficient to describe braid the entire braid behavior.

Multiple tubular braid samples were investigated to quantify braid angle change due to applied tensile loads. The braid angle investigation demonstrated that the braid angle change of the tubular braids varies around the circumference of the tubular braid samples. Variations in braid angle change may be

caused by combined loading between the end tabs or inconsistencies in the braid manufacturing process. The ability to view multiple regions around the braid circumference allows for the manufacturing consistency of the tubular braids to be evaluated.

Finally, the experimental setup was used to experimentally determine the longitudinal elastic modulus for tubular braid samples braided composites. A longitudinal elastic modulus of 17.41 ± 3.52 GPa was found for the tubular braid samples.

The experimental setup will further be used to experimentally determine the elastic constants for tubular braided composites. Tubular braids of varying geometry and material properties will be evaluated using this experimental setup.

6 References

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7 Figures

Fig 1: Tubular braided composites. Left: Kevlar49 braid preform. Right: Kevlar49 braid preform cured with Epon825/Ancamine1482

Fig 2: MTS tensile apparatus to measure strain and material properties of braided tubular composites

Fig 3: Applied displacement plot for the tubular braided composite test samples

Fig 4: Braid angle measurements (a) 0° (b) 30° (c) 60° (d) 90°

Fig. 5: Tubular braid surface(a) before applied tensile load (b) after applied tensile load

Fig 6: Tubular braid angle measurement (a) Braid angle before applied tensile load (b) braid angle after applied tensile load

Fig 7: Rectangular region to determine longitudinal strain of tubular braid samples

Fig 9: Examination of time dependency on the displacement of tubular braid samples for a constant applied force

Fig 8: Bulk motion of a tubular braid sample to verify the accuracy of the 3D DIC optical measurement

Fig 10: Transverse strain ϵ_{xx} along the longitudinal axis of a tubular braid sample (a) Maximum transverse strain ϵ_{xx} (b) Rotation stage position $\theta = 0^\circ$ (c) Rotation stage position $\theta = 30^\circ$ (d) Rotation stage position $\theta = 60^\circ$ (e) Rotation stage position $\theta = 90^\circ$

Fig 11: Longitudinal strain ϵ_{yy} along the longitudinal axis of a tubular braid sample (a) Maximum longitudinal strain ϵ_{yy} (b) Rotation stage position $\theta = 0^\circ$ (c) Rotation stage position $\theta = 30^\circ$ (d) Rotation stage position $\theta = 60^\circ$ (e) Rotation stage position $\theta = 90^\circ$

Table 1: Tubular braided composite maximum angle change due to applied load

Braid	Angle 0			Angle 30			Angle 60			Angle 90			Average	Standard Deviation
	Original	Final	$\Delta\theta$											
1	33.1	30.7	2.4	32.8	28.9	3.9	32.6	29.8	2.8	29.6	26.2	3.4	3.15	0.66
2	27.5	25.6	1.9	30.2	27.3	2.9	34.9	31.7	3.2	27.7	21.7	6	3.5	1.76
3	34.8	34.4	0.4	33.2	33.3	-0.1	32	33.4	-1.4	29.6	28.5	1.1	0.00	1.06
4	26.9	23.3	3.6	29.4	25.8	3.6	32.8	30.5	2.3	26.5	25.2	1.3	2.7	1.12
5	31.2	31	0.2	32.9	28.6	4.3	27.8	27.8	0	28.2	26.5	1.7	1.55	1.98
6	31.8	31	0.8	24.9	23.1	1.8	29.4	24.4	5	28.5	24.7	3.8	2.85	1.90
7	31.9	22.6	9.3	27.3	21.8	5.5	30.5	25.4	5.1	27.7	26.6	1.1	5.25	3.35
8	32.1	30.6	1.5	31.3	25	6.3	31.7	27	4.7	26.8	23.2	3.6	4.02	2.02
													2.88	1.58

Table 2: Tubular braided composite angle change prior to braid failure due to applied load

Braid	Angle 0	Angle 30	Angle 60	Angle 90	Average	Standard Deviation
	$\Delta\theta$	$\Delta\theta$	$\Delta\theta$	$\Delta\theta$		
1	1.2	1.9	0.3	0.2	0.9	0.80
2	1.8	0.4	0.4	0.8	0.85	0.66
3	0.8	1.8	0.8	1.1	1.125	0.47
4	2.2	0.7	0.1	0.2	0.8	0.97
5	2.6	1	0.6	2.4	1.65	1.00
6	0.7	0.4	4.2	3.5	2.2	1.93
7	1.9	0.8	3.5	0.7	1.725	1.30
8	0.2	0.6	0.9	1.2	0.725	0.43
Average	1.43	0.95	1.35	1.26	1.25	0.54

Table 3: Longitudinal elastic modulus for tubular braided composite samples

Braid	Angle 0	Angle 30	Angle 60	Angle 90	Average	Standard Deviation
1	21.87	22.04	22.94	21.26	22.03	0.69
2	17.56	18.73	19.12	19.15	18.64	0.75
3	12.32	11.16	11.09	11.71	11.57	0.57
4	18.38	19.08	19.48	21.09	19.51	1.15
5	19.90	18.68	18.29	16.95	16.95	1.22
6	18.03	19.24	19.86	20.61	19.43	1.09
7	10.98	13.17	13.17	14.24	12.89	1.37
8	19.46	18.74	17.86	17.03	18.27	1.06
Average	17.31	17.61	17.73	17.76	17.41	
Standard Deviation	3.76	3.58	3.81	3.45	3.52	